

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE: MCCT

COURSE CODE: ACA-401

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMARY OF ASSESSMENT

1. When do we not cite an author or a source in writing an academic paper?

- We do not need to cite a reference when we use any quote or paraphrase from another source.
- We do not need to cite an author when we use our ideas that an author has produced in our own words.
- We always must quote and indicate the source of information
- We do not need to cite when a piece of information we are writing about is common knowledge found in numerous areas.¹**

2. Which of the following statements is right about plagiarism?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic, 2019).

- We can take words or ideas from the internet without acknowledging them.
 - We cannot use a source of information without giving credit to the author of that information source.²**
 - Plagiarism is not a serious academic offense.
 - Plagiarism is wrong and unethical.²**
3. **In the context, the concept of opinions and facts of persuasive academic writing, which of the following statements is wrong?**
- Opinions state a personal view.
 - Opinions are the basis of influential people.³**
 - A fact is a specific statement that can be checked to be true.
 - The facts can be proven; they support the opinion.
4. **Turabian addresses that there are four different ways when citing sources like bibliographies (B), reference lists (R), notes (N), and parenthetical citations (P). Which out of the following four types represent the author-date style in academic writing?**
- P and R.⁴**
 - B and P.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 9

³ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*, 4th ed. (Wilmington, MA: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 292.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 129.

- R and N.
- B and N.

5. **Study reading strategies chose the correct answer?**

- We Start writing our understanding immediately without reading and thinking.
- Think before reading, ask yourself what you already know, and skim over the text.**⁵
- Pause during reading.**⁶
- Reflect after reading.**⁶

6. **Per Turabian, what are the common questions in academic work that researchers ask?**

- Conceptual questions: what should we think?
- Practical questions: what should we do?
- Applied questions: what must we understand before we know what to do?
- All the above mentioned.**⁶

7. **Preparation of citation gives the right answer according to Turabian?**

⁵ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*, 4th ed. (Wilmington, MA: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 334.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, 16.

- Use any sources
 - Record all bibliographical information before you take notes.**⁷
 - Do not record the page number for every quotation and paraphrase.
 - As you draft, clearly indicate every place where you do not need to cite a source.
8. **What is the difference between a reference list (R) and a bibliography (B) per the Harvard style?**
- There is no difference between the R and the B.
 - The R is a list of all the sources mentioned in the academic paper. In contrast, the B lists all sources used to help writing an assignment but not cited.**⁸
 - The B is a separate list following the R but in a different format.
 - The R and the B contain the same information but with switched author's or editor's surnames and first names.
9. **What is the correct principle of the European Commission?**
- The European Union acquires legal personality and absorbs the European Community.**⁹

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, 89.

⁸ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 59.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (Luxembourg: European Commission, 2020), 61.

- The European Council is made by all of the world institutions.
- The role of the European parliament can petition the Commission to put forward proposals.¹⁰**
- Under a new citizen's initiative, a citizen cannot petition the Commission to put forward proposals.

10. **According to Course pack Period 4, which is wright petroleum current uses in the economy fall?**

- Basic needs for basic living need necessary petrol, car.
- Capital needs capital structure to distribute energy and maintain a complex economy such as dams, electrical grids, refineries, roads, and bridges.¹¹**
- Future energy does not develop for the future.
- Discretionary, need for discretionary purposes such as vacation, entertainments, driving own cars instead of taking public transit for privacy and convenience.¹²**

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (Luxembourg: European Commission, 2020), 61.

¹¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 37.

¹² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 37.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.